

Alkali Metal Complexes : Infrared and Far Infrared Studies of Alkali Metal Acetylacetonates

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The close similarity of the spectra of the alkali metal acetylacetonates to those of transition metal acetylacetonates is evidence of the fact that the geometrical arrangement of acetylacetonate group around the metal atoms must be much the same for all the compounds.

Three sharp and intense vibrations observed for alkali metal acetylacetonates in the region 700-200 cm^{-1} further account for metal-oxygen bonding.

In the present work, we have studied the infrared and far infrared spectra of alkali metal acetylacetonates with the hope of providing important information about alkali metal-oxygen bonding.

Results and Discussion

All the alkali metal acetylacetonates have been prepared by the standard method of West¹. They are soluble in non-aqueous solvents.

Bellamy *et al.*^{2,3} observed that the first carbonyl band was shifted to the lower frequency in the spectra of the acetylacetonates of the transition elements. West and Riley² observed that ionic Cs.acac had a spectrum virtually identical with that of covalent Tl.acac. Lecomte⁴ noticed the similarity among spectra of covalent acetylacetonates, and this has been confirmed by us, even for all the alkali metal acetylacetonates.

If the alkali metal acetylacetonates had a purely ionic structure the C=O peak in these compounds would have appeared at a higher frequency, very near to that of acetylacetone (1725, 1705 cm^{-1}); instead, the absorption occurs between 1613-1595 cm^{-1} , near that found for the transition metal acetylacetonates¹. Acetylation of the OH group of enolized acetylacetone effectively removes the possibility of resonance and reduces the system to the simple conjugated C=C-C=O and shows bands at 1695 cm^{-1} . Further, it has been observed that lithium and sodium compounds of this kind became more covalent in their character when the alkali metal ions are complexed by two or more additional donor groups, e.g., water molecules¹.

The close similarity of the spectra of the alkali metal acetylacetonates to those of the transition metal acetylacetonates clearly indicate that the geometrical arrangements of the acetylacetonate groups around the metal atoms must be much the same for all the compounds. A qualitative relationship has been drawn between the strength of the metal-oxygen bond (the frequency of the perturbed

carbonyl absorption) and stability constant of transition metal acetylacetonates^{1,5}. Applying the same analogy to monovalent alkali metal acetylacetonates (Table 1), it is apparent that their metal-oxygen bonds are comparable to that of divalent metals^{1,5}.

TABLE 1—FREQUENCIES OF C=O BAND IN VARIOUS METAL ACETYLACETONATES (cm^{-1})

Metal	Frequency ^a	Metal	Frequency ^a
Ni(II)	1613	Cs(I)	1613
Mg(II)	1615	K(I)	1608
Cd(II)	1618	Na(I)	1604
Mn(II)	1607	Li(I)	1595
Co(II)	1595	Tl(I)	1610
Cu(II)	1580	Ag(I)	1612
Pd(II)	1577		

Three sharp and intense vibrations have been observed for the alkali metal acetylacetonates in the region 700-200 cm^{-1} . It is clear from Table 2 that the first strong absorption in the lower frequency region for acetylacetone is at 621 cm^{-1} and this band shifts to ~654 cm^{-1} in all the alkali metal acetylacetonates. This can be reasoned to be due to metal-oxygen vibrations in the metal acetylacetonates. This shift can be compared with the corresponding shift in the same region in case of rare-earth acetylacetonates, which have been categorised

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF ACETYLACETONE AND ALKALI METAL ACETYLACETONATES IN THE FAR INFRARED REGION (cm^{-1})

H.acac	Li.acac	Na.acac	K.acac
639 s	646 s	654 s	654 s
621 s			
510 s	528 s	522 s	519 s
472 w			
403 w	410 s	407 s	408 s
		395 s	394 s
364 w			
326 w	262 s	273 s	250 s

as true coordination compounds⁶. The second absorption band around 520 cm^{-1} shows small upward shift which can be explained by a weak metal-oxygen bond in such complexes. Regarding the third band around 410 cm^{-1} , which also shows a slight upward shift, this may be due to coupling of acetylacetonate vibrations within the complex.

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